

Tunneling Fundamentals, Practice and Innovations

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THE EFFECT OF HYBRID REINFORCEMENT OF RECYCLED TIRE FIBERS AND RECYCLED CARBON FIBERS ON THE PROPERTIES OF SELF CONSOLIDATING CONCRETE

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Outline

- Introduction
- Literature
- Research Objectives
- Scope of Work
- Methodology
- Test Results / Discussion
- Conclusion
- Next Steps
- Acknowledgements

Introduction

- Self-Consolidating Concrete (SCC), also known as self-compacting concrete
- High workability, flowability, passing ability and forming around reinforcement
- Specific mix proportioning as well as using admixtures:
 - Viscosity Modifying Admixture (VMA),
 - High Range Water-Reducing (HRWR) agent
- Fresh, hardened and durability properties of SCC
- Use of non-cementitious materials
- Fiber-reinforced SCC
- UTI applications

Traditional Concrete

Richard-Hulin et al. 2011

Self-Compacting Concrete

Literature

- Scrap tire is a state that vehicle's tire reaches its end of life.
- Although the tire reaches its end of service life as a vehicles tire, there are plenty applications that it still meets for the requirements.
- 4.2 Million tons of scrap tire are produced annually. (U.S. Tire Manufacturer Association, 2017)
- 81.4% is used in the market.
- 18.6% is not utilized yet. (781.2 thousands of tons)

Literature

- In concrete technology, scrap tire can be converted to several forms such as:
 - 1) Ground tire rubber
 - 2) Recycled tire steel fibers
 - 3) Recycled tire fibers (Tire Textile)

Literature

Tire Textile

Literature

- Carbon fibers can improve flexural and tensile strength and control drying shrinkage of cement based composite materials. (S. Akihama et al. 1986, P. Chen et al. 1993, D. Chung et al. 2000)
- Graham et al. (2017) studied the effect of micro and meso carbon fibers on the composite cement mortar. They recommended the idea of using hybrid fibers for improvement of both rheology and hardened properties.
- Shu et al. (2015), 2% and 4% carbon fibers with the length category of micro, macro and combination of both. Result showed that the hybrid fibers improve dispersion and tensile performance.
- Li et al. (2015) worked on the hybrid effect of 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 % carbon fiber and 5, 10 and 15% CaCO₃ whiskers. They showed that the hybrid effect out performs the mixtures with individual fibers.
- In a study performed by Chen and Chung (1993), a concrete mixture containing 0.5% virgin carbon fiber (by weight of cement) had 39% increase in the total price of the concrete.

Utilizing recycled carbon fibers

Literature

- Saccani et al. (2019) used shredded epoxy coated carbon fibers in order to make cementitious based composites. According to their results, a **decrease in workability** was observed but, **significant increase in flexural strength** and a transition from brittleness to semi-ductile behavior was reported.
- Rangelov et al. (2019) used low energy mechanically processed carbon fiber composite material in reinforcing pervious concrete. Recycled carbon fiber, increased the workability of the mixtures while decreasing the porosity as opposed to the previous literature reported on the regular cement mortar. The other observed effects were increasing infiltration rate, compressive strength and module of elasticity.
- There has not been any study yet investigating the effect of chemically recycled carbon fibers.

Research Objective

1. Investigate the effect of pyrolysis – chemically recycled carbon fibers on the performance of Self Consolidating Concrete for underground infrastructures.
2. Investigate the effect of Recycled Tire Fibers on the performance of Self Consolidating Concrete for underground infrastructures.
3. Investigate the effect of hybrid fibers on the performance of Self Consolidating Concrete for underground infrastructures.
4. Compare the hybrid effect versus the individual effects.

Scope of Work

- ✓ Phase I
 - Documentation and Information Search

- ✓ Phase II
 - Experimental Investigations
 - ✓ Fresh Concrete Properties
 - Rheology
 - ✓ Hardened Concrete Properties
 - Mechanical
 - ✓ Compressive/Tensile Strength
 - ✓ Durability
 - ✓ Drying Shrinkage
 - ✓ Bulk Electrical Resistivity
 - ✓ Water Absorption

- Phase III
 - Data Analysis
- Phase IV
 - Draft Final Report

Application
to UTC-UTI

- Sustainable Infrastructure Materials (Extending the Life)
- Avoiding Micro-Cracks (Extending the Life)
- Improved Load Bearing Capacity and Durability
- Improved Workability and Impact Resistance

Scope of Work

Methodology

SCC Mix Design Proportions

	Cement (kg/m ³)	Fly Ash (kg/m ³)	W/C	Water (kg/m ³)	Coarse Agg. (kg/m ³)	Fine Agg. (kg/m ³)	Air Voids %	SP	VMA
	422.8	126.8	0.49	207.2	541.2	718.8	-	-	-
% by weight	21.0	6.3	-	10.3	26.8	35.6	-	0.90*	1.02*
% by volume	14.1	5.5	-	20.7	21.8	28.0	10.0	-	-

*% by weight of cementitious materials

Mortar Mix Design Proportions

	Cement (kg/m ³)	Fly Ash (kg/m ³)	W/C	Water (kg/m ³)	Coarse Agg. (kg/m ³)	Fine Agg. (kg/m ³)	Air Voids %	SP	VMA
	468.4	-	0.5	234.2	-	1309.9	-	-	-
% by weight	23.2	-	-	11.6	-	65.0	-	1.80%	0.63%
% by volume	15.6	-	-	23.4	-	50.9	10.0	-	-

*% by weight of cementitious materials

Fiber Content: 0.5 % by weight of concrete

Methodology

SCC Mix Design Labeling

	Control	RTF	RTS	CF	CF+RTF	CF+RTS
Recycled Tire Fiber	-	0.05%	-	-	0.025%	-
Recycled Tire Steel Fiber	-	-	0.05%	-	-	0.025%
Recycled Carbon Fiber	-	-	-	0.05%	0.025%	0.025%

SCC Fresh Properties

Mix ID	J-ring Test		Slump Test		Segregation resistant	Penetration Test Blocking Assessment
	Diameter (cm)	T ₅₀ (s)	Diameter (cm)	T ₅₀ (s)		
Control	68.5	4.62	70.5	4.3	Moderately resistant	No visible blocking
RTS	54	26.9	57.8	15.9	Resistant	Minimal to noticeable blocking
RTF	63.5	8	66.5	7.4	Moderately resistant	Minimal to noticeable blocking
CF	-	-	-	-	Not resistant	Noticeable to extreme blocking
CF+RTF	-	-	-	-	Resistant	Noticeable to extreme blocking
CF+RTA	-	-	-	-	Resistant	Noticeable to extreme blocking

Mortar Slump Spread

Mix	Spread (cm)
Control	20.5
RTF	12
CF	12

Test Results / Discussion:

Compressive Strength

SCC

Mortar

Test Results / Discussion:

Split Tensile Strength

SCC

Test Results / Discussion:

Air voids

SCC

Mortar

Test Results / Discussion:

Water Absorption

SCC

Mortar

Test Results / Discussion:

Length Change

Mortar Length Change

Conclusion

1. Recycled Carbon Fiber negatively impacts the fresh properties of both concrete and mortar at high volume.
2. Recycled Tire Fiber does not change the compressive strength of mortar and concrete. Recycled Carbon Fiber may decrease compressive strength if it causes excess air voids. The mixture with hybrid fiber can be as strong as control mixture.
3. Recycled Tire Fiber decreases the split tensile strength but recycled carbon fiber has positive impact. The hybrid effect can revive the lost strength up to control sample.
4. Recycled carbon fiber increases the air content of the concrete mixture. This effect can still be observed in hybrid fibers. Recycled Tire Fiber may increase the air content when mixed with fine aggregates.
5. If the air content be controlled, recycled tire fiber and carbon fiber can increase durability both individually and hybrid.
6. Both fibers positively impact shrinkage control.
7. The mixture with hybrid fiber has better overall performance in hardened and durability properties.

Next Steps

1. Flexural strength evaluation
2. Bulk electrical resistivity evaluation
3. Fibers content optimization

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Q & A

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Thank You!